

STRATEGIC PLANNING AND STRATEGY SELECTION TECHNIQUES IN THE PROCESSES OF IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article covers issues of strategic planning and strategy selection techniques in the processes of improving the management of general secondary schools.*

Keywords: *general secondary education system, strategy, strategic planning, democratic management, state education standards.*

The management of the educational system is based on the formation of a management system based on democratic principles, which involves the implementation of the functional tasks of educational institutions, the coordination of the activities of the subjects of the general secondary education system, first and foremost, the selection of types of strategies, the determination of the ways of their improvement, developing and implementing new strategic plans aimed at implementing improved strategies [1].

In the process of managing the general secondary education system, the following several methods and forms of democratic management can be distinguished, which are important in the direction of encouraging subjects to achieve strategic goals and coordinating their activities in the process of achieving goals:

Management by goal-directed tasks - management in this method first of all sets tasks in the direction of achieving the goal on the basis of step-by-step at all levels, creates convenience in determining the methods and ways to achieve the goal based on a certain established procedure and plan, as well as the analysis of inspections and achievements;

management through employee involvement - ensuring the participation of employees in the process of goal formation, as well as its implementation and maintenance;

management by agreed goals is a form of mutual management through goal-directed tasks and employees' communication, in which employees participate in defining the goals that need to be achieved, and the directions for achieving current goals are agreed upon [2].

According to S.T.Turgunov, strategic management has its own characteristics, which are determined by the consistency of actions in achieving the goal, that is, these aspects are not determined by the goal in themselves, but mutual cooperation in achieving the goal, mutual understanding, effectiveness of the interaction process, favorable mental atmosphere in the team, conditions created for team members, because the main goal of the educational institution is common, and although it does not change, this goal is determined as a result of changes in time conditions and the composition of team members, the effectiveness of management activities may change [3].

Therefore, in order to organize strategic management processes, it is necessary to select types of strategies or to develop new ones based on their improvement, which implies the organization of the management process on a scientific basis and will be directed to the improvement of the system activity to ensure its effectiveness. The deadlines for the organization

of activities aimed at improvement, the functional tasks in the direction of their implementation and the deadlines for their implementation, the responsible subjects, the objects of implementation of the specified tasks are presented in the strategic plans. Strategic planning processes represent strategic planning processes [1]. We will focus on planning, strategic planning, types of strategies and the necessity of their improvement in order to clarify the essence and practical significance of these concepts.

Strategic planning processes have their own characteristics and can be implemented in several stages. In the process of organizing and managing the activities of general secondary schools, strategic planning is carried out in the following stages:

The first stage is the stage of selection and improvement of strategies, in which the types of strategies and their specific aspects are studied, the goals of each of them and in which directions they can be used are determined, and the strategies are improved according to the strategic goals.

In the clarifying stage, which is considered the second stage, the activity of the general secondary education system and the current state of the educational processes in educational institutions that are system components are studied, and it is determined which type of strategy is most needed to be implemented, and the implementation of strategies (primary and secondary) levels are defined.

The third stage is the stage of coordination according to the strategic goal, which includes defining the strategy of each educational institution according to the general goals and tasks of the general secondary education system, specifying the achievable results in advance, includes such processes as determining the factors affecting the performance of functional tasks, coordinating the tasks defined in the strategic plan with the capabilities of subjects and objects.

The fourth stage is the stage aimed at ensuring the content integrity of the activities of educational institutions and the educational processes in them, which are considered system components, and the activities of subjects and educational processes in accordance with the requirements specified in the documents of state educational standards and state requirements. focuses on coordination. Consistency and continuity are ensured in the performance of planned functional tasks in separate areas of activity of the components of the general secondary education system.

The fifth stage is considered the organizational stage, in which the strategic goal and the responsible persons who implement the tasks determined according to it are determined. Executive entities are selected under the leadership of managers, and objects for implementation of specified tasks or experiments are selected.

The sixth stage is the strategic decision-making process, in which strategy implementation tactics are determined. Decisions are made on the basis of suggestions and opinions of all subjects regarding the terms of implementation of strategic plans, designated officials and objects of its implementation.

Unlike current plans, the strategy provides insight into the field of pedagogical activity intended for the long term. Their duration depends on a number of factors: the purpose of the educational institution and its technology, the variability of the internal and external environment, the distribution of resources, etc.

The importance of implementing strategic planning is due to the following reasons:

1) strategic planning is an important component of the management and coordination system, which creates conditions for prospective development, allows making current decisions taking into account strategic goals;

2) in the implementation of program tasks aimed at fulfilling the most important priority tasks and directions of the socio-economic development of our country, strategic planning serves as a suitable tool for unifying the administrative and personnel forces of the educational institution in solving educational problems;

3) the strategic planning process allows strengthening the relations between the administration and employees of the educational institution and ensures that all forces in the educational system work in a single direction.

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